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Drivers for inter-city innovation networks across Chinese cities: Modelling physical versus intangible effects

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Abstract: Cross-region innovation is widely recognized as an important source of keeping long term regional innovation competence. A growing number of studies investigate the network structure and mechanism of cross-region innovation collaboration in various contexts. However, existing research mainly pays attention to physical effects, such as geographical distance and high-speed railway connections. These studies ignore the intangible drivers in a changing environment, the more digitalized society and the increasingly solidified innovation network structure. Thus, the focus of this study is on the determinants of innovation networks, especially the intangible drivers which have been largely neglected so far. We employ a long period city-level data of Chinese patents to trace innovation networks across Chinese cities. By including ICT gap and network structural effect into the general proximity framework, this paper explores the changing mechanism behind Chinese innovation networks from a new perspective. The results show that the structure of major innovation networks has changed obviously in China. As mechanism behind such evolvement, the results confirmed the increasingly important role of intangible drivers in Chinese inter-city innovation collaboration, when controlling for effects of physical proximity, such as geographical distance. Since digitalization and coordinated development are the mainstream trends in China and other developing countries, the inter-city innovation collaboration pattern in these countries will witness dramatic change under the influence of intangible drivers.

Introduction

Cross-region collaboration in innovation activities plays an important role in providing complementary knowledge and promoting knowledge transmission (Grillitsch & Nilsson, 2015; Morrison, Rabellotti & Zirulia, 2013). It is crucial to avoid regional lock-in and keep long term innovation vitality (Boschma, 2005). Previous work has evidenced its positive effect on improving regional innovation ability and innovation efficiency, in particular in times of rising costs for innovation, increasing uncertainty and risks, and rapidly changing global demand patterns (Breschi & Lenzi, 2016; Broekel, 2012; De Noni, Ganzaroli & Orsi, 2017; Maggioni, Nosvelli & Uberti, 2007). Therefore, the identification of drivers for cross-region interactions in innovation activities has become one of the main research issues, not only in a scientific context but also for policy (see Scherngell 2021 for an overview).

For instance, as the innovation policy in the European Union attaches great importance to coordinated knowledge creation (Hoekman, Frenken & Tijssen, 2010), an increasing number of studies have focused on cross-region innovation networks in the EU (Scherngell & Lata, 2013). But, also for other countries, we can observe an increasing interest in that direction, for example for China (see e.g., Jiang, Shi, Peng & Li, 2017) or for the US (see e.g., Zhao & Islam, 2017). Empirical studies typically have employed concepts and techniques from spatial interaction theory to explore drivers of cross-region innovation networks, often in relation to the proximity concept (Boschma, 2005). Here, special emphasis has been put on how different types of proximities, such as geographical proximity, but also technological, cultural, or institutional proximities affect collaborations in innovation activities between actors located in different regions.

However, previous research only scarcely accounts for new developments in innovation research, e.g. increasing digitalization, and some countries suffer from the usage of too rough spatial breakdowns for measuring innovation networks. This study intends to address this research gap by focusing on drivers of innovation networks that have been largely neglected so far, shifting attention to the role of intangible effects, next to traditionally addressed geographical ones. By intangible drivers, we refer to physically, non-graspable characteristics, such as network effects put forward by Neuländtner and Scherngell (2020), or effects related to the introduction of new digital technologies. Moreover, we focus on a very interesting geographical environment by directing our lens on China as a specifically interesting case, but as one of the first studies mobilizing spatially very detailed data at the level of Chinese cities, going beyond most previous works at the province level (see e.g., Scherngell & Hu, 2011).

Accordingly, the objective of this study is to estimate drivers for inter-city innovation networks across Chinese cities, specifically shifting attention to the role of intangible effects related to networks and digitalization. As China aims to be an innovation powerhouse globally and has adopted a series of policies to promote cross-region innovation collaboration, it provides an ideal context for the study of regional innovation collaboration in developing countries. In recent years, some researchers have chosen to study the structure and evolution of Chinese innovation networks at the province or city-level, but not at a relational level between these spatial entities (Sun, 2016; Sun & Cao, 2015; Xie & Su, 2021; Yao & Li, 2022). However, only a few studies explored the determinants of cross-region innovation collaboration, usually just focusing on specific industries and regions (Dong, Xu, Cheng & Sun, 2021; Li, Wei & Wang, 2015; Liu, Shao, Tang & Lan, 2021; Ma, Fang, Pang & Li, 2014), lacking city-level perspective (Pan, Pan, Ai & Guo, 2020; Scherngell & Hu, 2011), or ignoring long-term evolution of the mechanism (Jiang, Shi, Peng & Li, 2017).

This study departs from existing literature in the following major aspects. First, we take a dynamic global perspective to reveal the mechanism of forming a cross-region innovation collaboration network in China. The data we use is at the city level and covers all regions and industries. By using cross-sectional network data of four separate periods, we are able to compare the effect change of different determinants over time. Second, this paper provides new insights into the mechanisms of innovation collaboration networks. We integrate two kinds of intangible drivers into the general research framework, which are ICT and network structural effect. By this, we can make a deeper exploration to identify the mechanism of Chinese innovation network evolution.

Evolution of the innovation networks

We mobilize a large-scale database on Chinese patents to trace innovation networks across Chinese cities. In this section, we describe the data and the geographical setting in some more detail, and provide some descriptive insights into the evolution of the innovation networks in geographical space and over time.

Data and construction of the innovation networks

Since patents contain abundant and timely information about innovation, patent application data is widely used to measure innovation in China context studies (Dang & Motohashi, 2015). In particular, an invention patent needs a stricter requirement to be granted and has higher value than utility and design, hence, it can act as a better indicator for innovation. In this study, we use invention patent application data collected from the Chinese Patent Office (SIPO) to analyze the structure of the innovation collaboration network and the mechanism behind it. The dataset from SIPO has comprehensive information, except the address information of inventors. It only provides the residence address of the first assignee and the name of other assignees. Despite the limitation of SIPO data, it is still the most extensively used dataset in related studies. According to general practice in previous research, the information of co-assignees is used to analyze innovation collaboration in China (Hanley, Li & Wu, 2022; Sun, 2016; Sun & Cao, 2015; Xie & Su, 2021; Yao & Li, 2022).

The procedure of data screening and processing is as follows. Firstly, we selected patents that have more than one assignee, and excluded patents has individual assignees and non-mainland assignee¹. After this procedure, there are only three types of assignees in our sample: firms, universities and research institutions in mainland China. Then, we locate the exact city of each assignee with their name information. Finally, we construct city-by-city R&D collaboration matrices of every year by aggregating the number of individual co-patents to the city level.

To sum up, the study area contains 297 prefecture-level cities and above, which acted as the main participants of innovation in China. The study period covered the year from 2007 to 2018². Besides, in order to reflect the dynamic mechanism of innovation collaboration and reduce the impact of patent application data fluctuation, we divide the whole period into four periods (3-year time window), 2007-2009, 2010-2012, 2013-2015, 2016-2018. At last, we get four 297×297 matrices for each period; each element y_{ij} of the matrix represents the collaboration intensity between city i and city j in the corresponding period, given $i=j=1, \dots, 297$.

Overall network evolution

The innovation network has changed dramatically during the study period; it is becoming denser and more integrated (see Table A1 in Appendix). At the same time, the inequality of innovation collaboration is increasing (see Table A2 and A3 in Appendix).

The inequality of innovation collaboration is also reflected in Figure 1, which shows the spatial distribution of the degree centrality of China's intercity innovation network. Degree centrality measures the number of cities that a city has direct links to, it reflects a city's power to collaborate with others. As we can see, large differences exist between different cities' degree centralities. In the first period, most cities collaborate with less than ten cities, while Beijing and Shanghai are able to collaborate with 177 and 124 cities separately. In particular, Beijing dominates the innovation network during the whole period; its degree centrality has increased to 279 in the last period. That is to say, Beijing plays a crucial role in bridging cities

in the network. However, the figure also reveals that Beijing's dominant position has been weakened over time, as all cities are able to collaborate more with other cities. In the year of 2016 to 2018, approximately more than 85% cities have direct links with more than 10 cities. In which a majority of provincial capital cities and coastal cities (like Tianjin, Qingdao, Suzhou and Wuxi) have more than 100 innovation partner cities. As a result, the Gini index of degree centrality decreased obviously from 0.67 to 0.52, which means that gap of degree centrality between cities is narrowed.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of degree centrality of intercity innovation network in China

Figure 2 represents significant inter-city links the innovation network. In order to visualize the network structure more clearly, we only include city pairs with more than 300 collaborations. It is evident that the structure of the major innovation network is different in the first two period and the last period. During 2007 to 2012, connections between most cities are very weak. Several cities located in Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei Region, Yangtze-River Delta and Pearl River Delta are main players of intercity innovation. These cities overcome long-distance barriers and form a triangle structure of innovation connection in eastern China. Since 2012, the major network structure has undergone dramatic changes. Firstly, more and more cities participate in the collaboration of Beijing, not only the capital cities of the province but also some periphery cities (like Pingdingshan city in Henan province) and its surrounding cities

(like Langfang belongs to Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region). Second, there are some strong connections over short distances. Cities within Yangtze-River Delta and Pearl River Delta have begun to construct an intra-regional connection. Third, the main innovation channels show a diamond-shaped structure. Chengdu and Chongqing of the western region become a new vertex in the network, although this vertex's connection to others is still weak.

Figure 2. Spatial structure of intercity innovation network in China

Notes: Only observations with more than 300 collaboration links between any two cities are displayed

Methods

We set the spatial interaction model to study the determinants of innovation networks according to the work of Schergell and Hu (2011), among others. They mobilize a Negative Binomial version of the model due to the true integer nature, non-negative and very skewed distribution of the dependent variable observing innovation networks, in our case co-patenting between Chinese. The basic mechanics of the model relate to observed inter-city innovation intensities as reflected by the co-patents illustrated in the previous section to a set of origin city, destination city, and most importantly separation variables between two cities. Augmenting the typical setting, we introduce two intangible drivers into the model. The definition of variables can be seen as follows.

Intangible separation variables

- *ICT gap.* Considering data availability at the city-level, we choose three indicators in this paper: internet-broadband subscriptions (per 100 inhabitants), mobile-cellular telephone subscriptions (per 100 inhabitants), the ratio of telecom business revenue to GDP. Through principal component analysis, we construct an integrated ICT development index. In addition, we further normalize the index from 1 to 10. For the construction of the gap, we then divide the integrated ICT development index into 3 levels: the low level (1-4), the medium level (4-7), and the high level (7-10). If two cities are not in the same development level, then this variable is equal to 1, and 0 otherwise.
- *Gap in individual network centralities.* Following the work of Neuländtner and Scherngell (2020), we use the gap in degree centralities to estimate network structural effect. The degree centralities are calculated by the difference of collaboration links using accumulated network data. Considering that cross-city innovation collaborations are rare in the early period, the accumulated network is constructed from 2001. The variable is measured with one period lag to reduce the concern about the endogeneity problem.

Physical separation variables

- *Geographical distance.* We use the Euclidean distance between the geometric center of two cities to measure geographical distance. The intracity distance is measured as two-thirds the radius of a presumed circular with the same area as the city.
- *Technological distance.* Following the work of Scherngell and Hu (2011), the technological distance is measured as $1 - r^2$, where r equals the Pearson correlation coefficient between two cities' technological space vectors.
- *Same province dummy.* We add the same province variable into the basic model, it takes the value of 1 if two cities belong to the same province, and 0 otherwise.
- *High-speed railway dummy.* If two cities can be connected directly by a high-speed railway (HSR) without any transfer, then the variable takes the value of 1, and 0 otherwise.

As mass terms, we use the number of origin and destination cities' patent application (Marek, Titze, Fuhrmeister & Blum, 2017; Montobbio & Sterzi, 2013). Besides, according to related literature, we introduce ICT development variable as mass terms into the basic model (Rodríguez-Crespo & Martínez-Zarzoso, 2019; Wang & Choi, 2019). All the variables take log transformation, except binary variables.

Results

Table 1 represents the results of the spatial interaction models for different periods. The first column of each period is the estimation result for basic model, and the second column is the result that includes intangible drivers. Table 1 shows that we can indeed identify a statistically significant effect for intangible separation variables, and this effect tends to increase over time in magnitude. A higher ICT development gap negatively affects collaboration intensity between two regions, while a gap in degree centrality promotes cross-region collaboration significantly. In addition, ICT also shows a positive and significant impact on innovation collaboration. These results are robust when controlling for physical separation variables that are basically in line with previous literature, which indicates that the adding of two intangible drivers is reasonable and helps explain the formation of innovation network.

Turning to an interpretation of the main results, it turns out that – in line with previous literature – effects of physical proximity are significant, but change over time. The geographical distance is still a major barrier affecting research collaboration, its effect on R&D collaboration is negative and significant for all periods. The estimated coefficient of

technological distance is negative and significant for all periods and reaches the largest value in the last period. This finding is in line with the work of Liu, Shao, Tang and Lan (2021) that mainly focused on green technology, and the work of Balland, De Vaan and Boschma (2013) that take firms as units of analysis. The estimate for the same province dummy variable indicates that, even when controlling for geographical distance, firms or institutions still have strong tendency to collaborate with partners in the same province. This result has a strong correlation with Chinese innovation policy, as most of the innovation collaboration policy aims at providing support for firms or institutions in the same province for the maximization of local benefit. At last, the construction of a high-speed railway has obvious impact on R&D collaboration (Dong, Zheng & Kahn, 2020; Hanley, Li & Wu, 2022; Yao & Li, 2022). Although this effect is not significant for the first period, it turns to be positive and has an increasing trend for the following period. Regarding the insignificant effect in the first period, it may be caused by the lag-behind effect.

Turning to intangible effects, which is the main essence of this study, we can indeed identify a statistically significant effect for intangible variables, and this effect tends to increase over time in magnitude. Strikingly, the ICT development is highly significant, i.e. when two cities show a high development in ICT endowment, their collaboration intensity is likely to be increased. This effect strongly grows over the observed period, clearly outpacing the effects of the pure number of patents in a city. In terms of separation effects, this is confirmed, as a higher gap in ICT development has a negative effect on the collaboration intensity between two regions, and also this effect clearly increases over the observed periods. The gap in degree centrality positively influences the networking probability between two cities; an interesting pattern, on the one hand showing that it is important to control for network structural effects, and, on the other hand, pointing to a preferential attachment mechanism and hup-and-spoke structure of the network, i.e. central hub regions tend to attach emerging, peripheral region trying to enter the network.

Discussion

This study aims to explore the role of intangible drivers in the formation of inter-city innovation network in developing countries like China. We mobilize original data on inter-city innovation networks reflected in co-patents collected for the time period 2007-2018. A network analytical approach is used to explore the evolution of the innovation networks, while we specify spatial interaction models to estimate the relationship between collaboration intensity and intangible characteristics of the cities.

The initial results are promising. First, ICT gap among cities has negative effect, while the ICT development itself shows prominent role in promoting cross-region innovation collaboration. Second, the study reveals the existence of preferential attachment; the network structure has an increasingly positive effect. The result has great importance for analysing future innovation collaboration pattern in China. As the Chinese government has launched a wave of digital infrastructure construction since 2020. Especially, it pays much attention to the balanced development of digitalization in western regions. In 2022, China approved the construction of eight national computing hubs, of which five hubs are located in the western region. ICT development will reshape Chinese economic geography in the near future. The balanced development of ICT may give periphery regions more opportunities to access external knowledge. Apart from this, the network structural effect gives some thinking on how to change the unbalanced collaboration among regions in China. Like what is happening in some leading regions like Yangtze River Delta, local government should take more

measures to build cross-region innovation platforms and construct cooperation framework agreements to promote coordinated regional innovation.

Table 1. Estimation results

	2007-2009		2010-2012		2013-2015		2016-2018	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
<i>Origin and destination variables</i>								
Number of patents	0.986*** (0.0149)	0.800*** (0.0199)	0.956*** (0.0125)	0.683*** (0.0149)	1.004*** (0.0111)	0.711*** (0.0124)	0.691*** (0.00769)	0.493*** (0.00711)
ICT development		0.590*** (0.0856)		0.957*** (0.0697)		1.344*** (0.0630)		2.788*** (0.0581)
<i>Separation variables</i>								
Geographical distance	-0.482*** (0.0484)	-0.504*** (0.0488)	-0.500*** (0.0405)	-0.543*** (0.0401)	-0.583*** (0.0373)	-0.681*** (0.0378)	-0.523*** (0.0326)	-0.719*** (0.0340)
Technological distance	-0.177*** (0.0125)	-0.269*** (0.0145)	-0.180*** (0.0118)	-0.344*** (0.0134)	-0.170*** (0.0117)	-0.364*** (0.0133)	-0.562*** (0.0185)	-0.459*** (0.0140)
Same province dummy	1.616*** (0.116)	1.546*** (0.117)	1.661*** (0.101)	1.614*** (0.101)	1.812*** (0.101)	1.633*** (0.0974)	1.721*** (0.0970)	1.409*** (0.0872)
HSR dummy	0.316 (0.230)	0.306 (0.217)	0.223** (0.106)	0.285*** (0.0977)	0.373*** (0.0915)	0.401*** (0.0834)	1.074*** (0.0861)	0.683*** (0.0777)
Gap in ICT		0.0711 (0.0675)		-0.100** (0.0500)		-0.113** (0.0444)		-0.214*** (0.0381)
Gap in degree centrality		0.287*** (0.0237)		0.471*** (0.0215)		0.502*** (0.0192)		0.516*** (0.0165)
Constant	-11.94*** (0.388)	-11.60*** (0.386)	-11.80*** (0.329)	-11.92*** (0.322)	-12.60*** (0.305)	-13.49*** (0.308)	-8.723*** (0.261)	-15.41*** (0.290)
Dispersion	0.436*** (0.0493)	0.289*** (0.0513)	1.032*** (0.0318)	0.758*** (0.0346)	1.373*** (0.0242)	1.086*** (0.0260)	1.791*** (0.0208)	1.319*** (0.0217)
Likelihood ratio								
Observations	43,956	41,905	43,956	41,905	43,956	41,905	43,956	41,905

Notes: Several cities in Tibet Autonomous Region and Hainan province lack ICT infrastructure data. The number of cities included is 289. The sample of every period is $(289 \times 287) / 2 + 289 = 41905$.

Endnotes

¹ Because this study mainly focuses on city innovation in mainland China, thus we excluded patents that has assignees from Hongkong, Macao, Taiwan and other foreign countries. Besides, we can't find the location of individual assignees only with their name information, we excluded this kind patents from our analysis.

² The data before 2007 are deleted because of the small proportion of co-patent. The total amount of invention patent application during we have collected is 8,819,808 (during 2007 to 2018), which is close to the announced amount. Of all the patents we have collected, 663,770 were joint invention patent applications with at least two assignees. After data screening, the total amount of co-patent in our study is 462,002.

Appendix

Table A1. Overall network characteristics of intercity network from 2007 to 2018

Period	Number of nodes	Sum of edges	Average distance	Network Density	Average Degree
2007-2009	256	3086	2.279	0.047	12.008
2010-2012	288	5368	2.069	0.065	18.639
2013-2015	294	7566	1.950	0.088	25.795
2016-2018	297	9934	1.918	0.114	33.541

Note: The number of total city pairs is 43,956 ($=297 \times 296 / 2$).

Table A2. Descriptive statistics on innovation collaborations

Period	Observations	Sum	Mean	SD	Gini
2007-2009	1543	13234	8.58	50.70	0.7723
2010-2012	2684	36665	13.66	78.92	0.8145
2013-2015	3783	103096	27.25	166.35	0.8713
2016-2018	4967	149471	30.09	189.43	0.8712

Note: This table only shows descriptive statistics of city pairs have positive links.

Table A3. Quantile values of innovation collaborations

Quantile	2007-2009	2010-2012	2013-2015	2016-2018
1%	1	1	1	1
5%	1	1	1	1
10%	1	1	1	1
25%	1	1	1	1
50%	2	2	3	3
75%	4	6	9	10
90%	12	19	34	39
95%	23	41	79	90
99%	101	207	482	504
100%	1227	2593	4951	6174

Note: This table only shows descriptive statistics of city pairs have positive links.

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